

Soil Carbon Status of SRUC Platforms

Assessing the soil carbon storage and stability of samples collected from agricultural research platforms across Scotland

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Introduction

The work package of M8/M9 includes assessing the soil carbon storage and stability of samples collected from agricultural research platforms across Scotland.

In conjunction with C2, the unique network of experimental platform research sites within SRUC were sampled and these will be used to baseline the soil carbon status of these soils. The same fields in these platforms will be sampled in five years to estimate the effect of management on carbon soil carbon status.

Methods

The sampling was outsourced to **AgriCarbon**, an all-inclusive sampling and analysis company out of Dundee.

Analysis includes stratification for optimum randomisation for C inventorying, bulk density, Dumas dry combustion C.

Optional analysis includes routine soil analysis (NPK, pH, texture).

Soil cores up to 1 metre depth.

Sampling sites

SRUC experimental platforms:

- ACE, Aberdeen (pHoenix and Tulloch Rotational Trial)
- Kirkton and Auchtertyre Hill and Mountain Research Centre
- Dairy Research Centre, Crichton and Barony
- SRUC's Beef and Sheep Research Centre, Easter Howgate

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Implications

- These sites cover a wide range of climatic conditions and agricultural management systems across Scotland and provide extensive historical data and management information.
- Project outputs will inform relevant policies regarding soil carbon sequestration and climate mitigation. Such policies include Scottish Climate Change Adaptation Programme, Land Use Strategy, Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019, and Climate Change Plan.
- The results of the sequestration analysis will inform UK GHG inventory reporting.